

A Comprehensive Review of Gas Chromatography: From Fundamental Concepts to Advanced Hyphenated Techniques

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ABSTRACT

Gas chromatography (GC) is a powerful and versatile analytical technique first developed by Martin and James in 1952, now widely employed across pharmaceutical, environmental, food science, forensic, and clinical fields. This review provides a comprehensive overview of the fundamental principles, instrumentation, and applications of gas chromatography. The separation mechanism relies on the differential distribution of volatile analytes between a mobile carrier gas phase and a stationary phase within a column, with retention time serving as a characteristic parameter for compound identification. Key components of GC systems—including injection modes (split, splitless, on-column, and PTV), column types (capillary and packed), stationary phase classifications, and carrier gas selection—are discussed in detail. A systematic account of conventional and advanced detectors is presented, covering ionization-based detectors (FID, ECD, TID, PID, BID), bulk physical property detectors (TCD), optical detectors (FPD, AED, GPCD), molecular spectroscopic detectors (GC-FTIR, GC-VUV), and hyphenated techniques such as GC-MS and GC-IMS, each evaluated for their sensitivity, selectivity, and application scope. Advanced methodologies including pyrolysis GC, thermal desorption GC, multidimensional GC, and headspace extraction techniques are also reviewed. The application of GC in food analysis—encompassing fatty acids, aroma compounds, pesticide residues, and contaminants—is highlighted. This review underscores the continued evolution of GC technology and its indispensable role in modern analytical chemistry.

Keywords: Gas chromatography, volatile organic compounds, detectors, capillary column, GC-MS, multidimensional chromatography, food analysis

INTRODUCTION

HISTORY:

Modern gas chromatography (GC) was invented by Martin and James in 1952. Martin, in his award address, suggested it might be possible to use a vapor as the mobile phase. Some years later, James and Martin used ethyl acetate vapor to desorb the moisture of fatty acid that had been fixed to an adsorbent and placed in a tube. The vapor stream eluting from the tube was directed to an automated titration apparatus, resulting in a graph showing a series of “steps” that reflected the sequential additions of base as each eluted acid was neutralized by automated titration. Erika Cremer, and Australian scientist during the

period of the second world war, had published article based on the gas chromatography. It was the period when women were expected to confine their activities to children, church, and kitchen. So, her work on GC was appreciated by many scientists, especially in 2008 when Leslie Etter published an article of her concluded that her arguments and theoretical basis of GC were acceptable. The work with detectors was highly productive. The electron capture detector (ECD) was developed by Lovelock, responding only to molecules that reduced the flow of electrons generated as a stream of β -particles. The specificity of the detector allows sensitivities for the alkali flame detector for nitrogen, which enables specific and sensitive detection of nitrogen containing molecules. As many pharmacologically active molecules do

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contain nitrogen atoms, this was an ideal detector for the analysis of drugs in biological fluids.

Principles Of Gas Chromatography:

The basis of the separation is a retardation of the individual components as they are moved through a long column by a carrier gas, usually helium or nitrogen. The column consists of a steel or glass tube. The sample is injected into the carrier gas stream. As it moves through the column with the carrier gas, the molecules of each substance present in the sample will distribute between the gas and the liquid. The more volatile a substance, the greater proportion of time its molecules will be moving in the carrier gas, and so the sooner it will emerge from the column. In this way, each substance will become separate within the column and emerge separated by time at the end. The time taken from the injection to emergence is known as the retention time [Rt] and is characteristic for each substance under any given set of conditions. It depends on the volatility of the substances, as well as the temperature of the column and its length and diameter. Many substances have an inconveniently

long retention time at room temperature, and this is overcome by heating the column in an oven. Having separated the components in the column so that they emerge individually, some method of detecting and measuring them is needed. Two types of detectors are commonly used: Thermal Conductivity Detector [TCD] and Flame Ionization Detector [FID]. Thermal Conductivity Detectors [TCDs] rely on changes in the thermal conductivity of the gas leaving the column. The pure helium gas carrier gas passes through the column since helium has very high thermal conductivity. The Flame Ionization Detector [FID] is mostly used in food applications. The gas emerging from the column is burned with a hydrogen and air mixture. This forms ions, which conduct an electric current, which can be amplified and recorded on a chart recorder. Although the number of ions formed in this way is small, perhaps only 0.0001 percent of the total carbon atoms present in the sample, the proportion produced is always constant. This means that the total signal recorded on the chart recorder is proportional to the amount of chemical substances present.

Fig 1: Schematic diagram of Gas chromatography

Note: Figures in this article were generated using AI-assisted tools and edited by the authors

Analysis Of Volatile Organic Compounds Used In Gas Chromatography:

Volatile organic compounds [VOCs] are involved in many fields such as food, Flavors and fragrances, medical and forensic science. The main area dealing with VOCs may be environmental chemistry, because VOCs contribute to stratospheric ozone depletion,

tropospheric ozone formation, toxic and carcinogenic human health effects, etc.

Sample Injection:

Sampling and pretreatment result in target VOCs in different physical states, being gaseous, dissolved in a liquid, trapped cryogenically, or adsorbed on a solid material. VOCs have been brought onto the GC column. Injection of liquid or gaseous sample is typically carried out by syringes and sample loops employing column, split and split less injection, for

solvents, large volume injection has been developed to improve limits of detection. A major difficulty with large volume liquid injections of VOCs is the limited difference in volatility solvents and analytes.

Separation:

Volatile Organic Compound have typically been separated on capillary columns, mainly silicon type wall coated open tubular column [WOCT] and

alumina based porous layer open tubular columns for highly volatile compounds.

Detection:

Capillary GC analysis of VOCs typically employs FID, MSD [Mass Spectrometry Detection], ECD [Electron Capture Detection], PID [Photo Ionization Detection], FPD [Flame Photometric Detection] and NPD [Nitrogen Phosphorous Detection].

Table 1: Four levels of speed in capillary gas chromatography [CGC]

Level	Description	Speed of relative analysis	Column dimensions	Inlet pressure (psg)	Injector	Detector
1	Conventional CGC	1	10-100m × 0.1-0.53mm	2-100	conventional	conventional
2	Rapid CGC on conventional instruments	3-5	5-50m × 0.18-0.53mm	2-100	Conventional, PTV cold trapping	Conventional sampling rates at 50Hz
3	High speed CGC on modified conventional instruments or components	5-10	2-25m × 0.10-0.25mm	10-150 or higher	Rapid heating	Conventional, sampling at 200Hz
4	Very high speed CGC in specialized instrument	10-50	2-10m × 0.003-0.10mm	20-200 or higher	nil	High sensitivity, high speed

Column Classification and Structure Retention Relationships Stationary Phase Classification

There are two types of columns, single-value scale and multiple value scales. The single value scale is based on polarity, and multiple value scales are based on selectivity. Column rankings are based on polarity. The stationary phase is defined as its relative capability to intermolecular interactions. Such as induction and hydrogen bonding. The columns are grouped according to their monomer chemistry. The selectivity of the ionic liquid stationary phases can be compared with the polar non-ionic stationary phases. A general strategy is the minimum number of stationary phases from different selectivity groups that span the selectivity space as evenly as possible.

Solvation Parameter Model

It is a fundamental model based on the parameterization of the cavity model of solvation. The appropriate form of the solvation parameter model for retention in gas-liquid chromatography is important.

Structure-Retention Relationships

Single Retention:

Direct connection between a distribution constant and a thermodynamic of solute interactions. It is simpler to measure. Relative retention measurements seem more attractive. Although retention time is both simple to measure and reasonable, and it is not directly related to the thermodynamic model of system. Relative retention measurements seem more attractive, therefore, for the development of shared user retention databases for compound identification.

Isothermal Retention Index:

Separations based on the wide temperature range with stationary phases of different polarities. Consequently, no single substance can fulfil the role of a universal standard, and in those cases where the retention of the sample and standard are markedly different, accuracy would be impaired. Which the retention index of any substance is equal to 100 times

the carbon number of a hypothetical n-alkane with the same adjusted retention time of retention factor, partition constant.

Capillary Column:

Capillary columns were introduced in 1959 but not used widely about 1980. It is the simple columns with open tubes, but they are not filled with packing material, such columns are called as “open tubular (OT)”

Types Of Capillary Column:

1. Wall-Coated Open Tubular Column (WCOT)

It consists of a glass tube with a thin film of liquid phase coated on the inside surface. This is called a wall coated open tubular column (WCOT). This tube is made up of glass or stainless steel, fused silica. Tubing diameters of 0.10, 0.20, 0.25, 0.32 mm are commercially available. Column length varies from 10 to 60 m, although it is 100 m columns.

2. Support-Coated Open Tubular Column (SCOT)

It contains an adsorbed layer of very small solid support such as Celite coated with a liquid phase. The

liquid phase has a higher sample capacity than thin films common to the early WCOT columns.

3. Porous Layer Open Tubular Column (PLOT)

It contains a porous layer of a solid adsorbent such as alumina and molecular sieve; columns are well suited for the analysis of light fixed gases and other volatile compounds. Carbon monoxide and methane. This column allows separations combining adsorption chromatography with high resolution capillary columns. The adsorbent is coated on the inside wall of the capillary. These columns can be challenging to make. Top-quality PLOT column is being used; it is always best practice to have a mechanism in place to catch any eluting particles. Plot columns will always have a higher restriction simply because the column has lower permeability due to the adsorption layer. This factor is used to test product quality in the process. It is quite different from liquid-phase coated columns. Liquid-phase columns mainly involve dissolving a polymer in a suitable solvent. Capillary tubing is primarily available in fused silica capillary tubing. ID tubing is used and coated with 10-50 μm layers of adsorbent. In addition to fused-silica tubing, PLOT columns are also available in metal tubing.

Fig 2: WCOT, SCOT, PLOT columns

Column Selection:

The five critical parameters for capillary columns.

1. Internal Diameter

Fused silica of internal column diameters ranges from 100 to 530 μm . Limited sample capacity and are not well suited for trace analysis. Some capillary columns have 250 or 320 μm diameters. It represents the best compromise between resolution, speed,

sample capacity. $250\mu\text{m}$ is a good starting point for method development.

2. Column Length

Plate number, N is directly proportional to column length; retention time R_t , is also proportional to column length. Long columns have more theoretical plates, and the better the separation and resolution. The length of the column is 60m. Short columns have (5-10) for analysis of simpler samples. Medium columns are (15-10m). They provide a good compromise between resolution and speed analysis.

3. Film Thickness

The thickness of the column is $0.25\mu\text{m}$ and a good compromise between the high resolution with thin films. Thick films are increased retention of sample components and efficiency decreased. The thin films are more resolution and efficiency ($0.2\mu\text{m}$).

4. Stationary Phase

Liquids or very viscous polymers are used. The liquid phase must be high selectivity, α , for the compounds of interest. There are two types of liquid phase-in use today. Such as Diethyl polysiloxane, Dimethyl polysiloxane, Diphenyl dimethyl polysiloxane proprietary phase, Diphenyl dimethyl polysiloxane.

5. Carrier Gas and Flow Rate

Nitrogen is the carrier gas of choice since the Van Demeter B term dominates; nitrogen being heavier than helium minimizes this B term and produces more efficiency. Hydrogen provides a much faster analysis with minimal loss in efficiency.

Packed Column:

Packed columns are inert, and any liquid of low volatility can be handled in packed columns. This liquid is employed as a stationary phase. Packed columns are also better suited to handling samples containing a significant amount of involatile or thermally unstable matrix compounds.

Fig 3: Packed column

Types of Gas Chromatography Based On Stationary Phase:

1. Gas-Liquid Chromatography:

These are prepared by coating a support with the desired liquid phase and transferring the coated support to an empty column for the separation. Columns are made up of glass, stainless steel or nickel tubing and connect with the injector and detector inlets. Since stationary phases are frequently used,

such as hydrocarbon and perfluorocarbons, ether and polyesters, and chiral stationary phases. The lower operating temperature is usually close to the melting point of the stationary phase, and it is determined by the thermal stability of the stationary phase. Polyethylene glycols are widely used for the separation of volatile polar compounds and have good support for deactivating properties.

Classification of Stationary Phase

It is based on their solvent strength, polarity, and solvent selectivity. Single value scales of solvent strengths are unable to provide information and are used for column selection. The transfer of a solute from the gas phase to the stationary phase occurs in three steps:

1. Cavity formation
2. Transfer of solute to the cavity
3. Solute-solvent interaction

2. Gas-Solid Chromatography:

They are used as normal operating temperatures such as separation of gases, solvents and volatile hydrocarbons, and halocarbons. The carrier-gas can play a significant role in the separation process by competing with analyte molecules for adsorption at active sites on the stationary phase. Some examples of stationary phase such as

Table 2: Examples of stationary phase

S No	Features	Examples
1	Inorganic oxides	Silica gel, Alumina
2	Carbon adsorbents	Graphitized carbon blacks
3	Molecular sieves	Calcium aluminosilicate, sodium aluminosilicate
4	Porous organic polymers	Chromosorb 101, chromosorb 102

Sample Introduction In GC:

Injection of a sample into the gas stream at the column of a syringe and a hypodermic needle. A re-sealable rubber "Suba seal" cap was employed; this was replaced as early as 1964 by a heart resistant elastomeric septum compressed in a metal fitting. Injection of are presentative part of the sample as a narrow band in a quantity consistent with the capacity of the capillary column. The splitter injector volatilized the sample to enter the column. The injection of 20-100 μ L liquid volumes in routinely possible, rather than the formerly standard 1-2 μ L, by using sample introduction systems, such as on-column, 100 μ type and programmed temperature vaporization (PTV).The conventional splitting injection used to allow large volumes of a dilute sample solution to be introduced into the column. Technique routinely used in environmental analysis, analysis of pesticides in foods, and drug screening. The use of syringe for on-column injection into a wide-bore capillary was first described by Zlatkis in 1963. The specialized sample-introduction systems become capillary GC, including the PTV injector and pyrolyzed systems. PTV injectors can be used in split, split less, or direct mode. Low levels of volatile organics in environmental matrices may be analysed by headspace, dynamic stripping or purge, and trap sampling. The sample is purged with helium and volatile analytes collected on a trap of adsorbent material; they are released by rapid heating.

Sample Preparation

Direct injection is suitable for the analysis of simple mixtures of thermally stable compounds. Samples are dilute and require concentration. Samples contain in volatile compounds, such as inorganic salts, particulate matter, and polymeric materials.

Steps For Combination Of Technique To Prepare A Complex Sample Or Effective Separation:

1. Preliminary sample fractionation
2. Isolation of target compounds
3. Concentration to a level suitable for detection.

METHODS:

Isolation and Concentration Techniques Using Physical Methods

1. Traditional Methods:

It is a conventional technique. It is contemporary trends in ample preparation but to facilitate batch process. Distillation is a suitable technique for isolation. Compounds are low volatility and become suitable for analysis of direct injection most of the techniques is simple distillation and fractional distillation.

2. Solvent Extraction:

It is the most common technique for gases, vapor, and liquids. The target compound and their matrix have different solubilities and the distribution of samples between immiscible solvents.

Uses:

It depends upon the ratio of the extraction solvent and sample volume. Distribution constant should be large since there are practical limits to the phase volume.

3. Gas Phase Extraction:

It is used to isolate compounds that are difficult to recover from sorbent traps. It is the most common method for isolating volatile organic compounds and maximizing the surface contact between the gas and liquid phase by the continuous stream of freely dispersed bubbles.

4. Solid Phase Extraction:

It is based on the transfer of a target compound from a gas or liquid sample. The surface of the solid is intimate contact with the sample. The sorbent is separated from the sample matrix by various means. The target compounds recovered by solvent elution.

Pyrolysis Gas Chromatography

Fig 4: Pyrolysis in GC

Types of Pyrolyzers:

The three most used recognized pyrolyzers for GC are the microfurnace, curie-point and resistively heated filament. The "Microfurnaces" rapidly rise the temperature of the sample until the pyrolysis temperature is reached and then maintains this

GC is used routinely to analyse complex substances such as tire, rubber, textiles, dried, paint, glue paper coatings, petrochemical sources, plant material, coal, bacteria, and of course, the whole range of synthetic polymers. Pyrolysis has been used extensively over the last 20 to 30 years as an analytical technique in which large molecules are degraded into smaller volatile species using only thermal energy. The ultimate objective of analytical pyrolysis is to use the chromatographic information of pyrolysis products to determine the composition or structure of the original sample pyrolysis, combined with modern analytical methods, such as gas chromatography.

Pyrolysis GC Technique:

The standard configuration of a pyrolysis GC instrument has been a pyrolysis device or pyrolyzer, which is interfaced with an analytical column of GC via the injection port. A flow of inert gas such as nitrogen or helium, flushes, the pyrolyzes into the column, where components are separated. Such developments include the use of lasers as a fragmentation source and more recently a technique called in column or non-discriminating pyrolysis. This constant refinement of instrumental devices and parameters during the past 20 years provides an expensive record on the pyrolysis of polymers.

temperature for the desired pyrolysis time. The samples are either injected or dropped into the pyrolysis zone by liquid syringe, solid plunger syringe, or by using a small cup. The desired characteristics of this type of pyrolyzer, such as reproducibility, have always been difficult to develop.

Curie Point

Accurately reproduce pyrolysis condition using ferromagnetic metals. The sample, which is positioned on to the end of a pyrolysis wire made Froman appropriate ferromagnetic alloy, is inserted into the pyrolizer and rapidly heated using a high frequency induction coil. In the temperature ceases to rise when the curie point of the metal has been reached, that is exactly reproducible temperature at which the ferromagnetic material loses its magnetism. At this point, the temperature remains constant until the coil is switched.

Filament Pyrolyzers

Filament pyrolyzers can acquire a controlled pyrolysis temperature extremely quickly by using a piece of resistive metal. An initial pulse of heating at a high voltage produces a current through the causing the filament to heat rapidly until the programmed pyrolysis temperature is reached. The pyrolysis temperature is maintained by reducing the voltage.

Thermal Desorption Of GC

Atmosphere particulate matter (PM) or atmospheric aerosol are tiny pieces of solid or liquid matter suspended in the atmosphere. TD is facilitated to be online coupled with a modified GC injector, leading to direct sample injection and extremely low sample loss to approximately zero. The TD method is by directly inserting the sample filters into the injector linear tube of GC for desorption. The rise of the injector port temperature to 275° required 11min and the heating rate could not be controlled precisely. The device could be placed on the top of a GC injector directly and coupled to GC for quantitative and qualitative analysis. Blank measurements were carried out for both filters and aluminium foil used as substrates for PM sample collection. The paper filter compounds with lower boiling points were no longer detected during the second desorption. The signals of higher boiling point compounds became stronger, and some new unidentified peaks appeared. The aluminium foil showed a different pattern some compounds were absent in the second run, resulting in a much cleaner and lower background signal. Aluminium foil was chosen as the supporting material for PM sample analysis.

Fig 5: Thermal Desorption Gas Chromatography (TD-GC) System and Process

Multidimensional Gas Chromatography:

Multidimensional high resolution coupled to a GC column is used for the separation of complexes in industry and environmental analysis. The main purpose of coupling is to increase the peak capacity of the separation unit and the speed of analysis. The first approach of GC coupled columns was used in crude

oil and refinery products in 1960, aiming to achieve a high degree of deconvolution with the two column systems. Multidimensional chromatography involves the use of more than one column to perform the separation of a single sample and is usually performed by collecting an aliquot of the effluent from the first column and injecting it onto a second column with involving the speed of separation, precision, accuracy,

and selectivity. Multidimensional separations involving GC can employ two GC columns. To carry out such different chromatographic techniques-Liquid chromatography - (LC-GC), (LC-LC) etc.....

Principle

The principle involved in the MDGC is a comprehensive two-dimensional (2D) gas chromatography (GC x GC). It employs various compositions of the mobile phase and stationary phase. The effluent is transferred after initial

separation to another column for the final separation. A high peak capacity is one of the objects of MDGC.

Heart Cutting

It is a simple fraction from the collection of the first column and reinjecting it into the second column. It's separate from one or a few critical peak pairs or groups. but it's not effective in the first column. The modulator used is Deans Switch. It is a flow modulator device.

Fig 6: Multidimensional Gas Chromatography

Comprehensive Two-Dimensional Gas Chromatography:

It differs from GC with heart cutting in that the second – dimension chromatogram is sampled continuously throughout the chromatographic run. It has two columns with a press-fit connector and modulator present between them. It has been constructed within the oven of a traditional gas chromatograph with an

existing inlet and detector. The first dimension is a capillary column, and the second dimension is short, smaller-diameter capillary column within an independent. Thermal modulation consists of four pneumatically controlled jets, placed at the head of the second column. Two cold jets and two hot jets. Which uses hot nitrogen or air to rapidly cool and then heat the head of the second column.

Fig 7: Comprehensive Two Dimensional Gas Chromatography

Headspace In Gas Chromatography:

In gas chromatography (GC), Headspace refers to the vapor phase that exists above a liquid or solid sample inside a sealed container. Instead of injecting the liquid or solid directly into the GC, the vapor above the sample is analysed. This vapor contains the volatile compounds from the sample.

Headspace Extraction:

1. Static Headspace Extraction:

The sample is sealed in a vial and heated until equilibrium is reached between the sample and vapor phase. A portion of the vapor is then withdrawn and injected into the GC. It is simple, widely used, and suitable for concentration ranging from percent to parts per billion. Multiple headspace extraction is a variation used for lower concentration.

2. Dynamic Headspace Extraction:

Also known as purge and trap, an inert gas flows through or over the sample, carrying volatile compounds to a sorbent trap for collection before GC analysis. It is mainly used for trace-level analysis.

3. Sorptive Extraction:

Many static headspace extraction (SHE) methodologies use a sorbent material to capture analytes before they are introduced into the gas

chromatograph (GC), rather than transferring only the vapor directly.

In some techniques, the sorbent is placed inside the sample vial

4. Headspace solid phase microextraction

5. Stir- bar sorptive extraction

6. Single drop microextraction

Various Detectors Used In Gas Chromatography:

A. Conventional Detectors For GC:

Gas chromatography (GC) employs a variety of detectors to identify and quantify components of volatile organic compounds. These detectors are categorized based on their detection mechanisms into ionization-based detectors, bulk physical property detectors, optical detectors, and electrochemical detectors. Each detector type has unique operational principles, advantages, limitations, and specific applications.

1. Ionization-Based Detectors:

Ionization detectors function by generating ions from neutral analyte molecules, which are then detected as electrical signals. These detectors are widely utilized due to their sensitivity and selectivity, especially for organic compounds.

1.1 Flame Ionization Detector (FID):

Principle: Organic compounds in the GC effluent are burned in an oxygen-hydrogen flame, producing ions that generate an electrical current proportional to the carbon content.

Operating Conditions: Typical temperatures exceed 250°C to prevent water condensation. Pure gases free of organic contaminants are essential.

Key Features:

1. Highly sensitive to hydrocarbons; non-carbon compounds are not detected.
2. Exhibits the “equal per carbon rule”, where response is proportional to carbon number; heteroatoms (O, N) reduce sensitivity.
3. Flow rates of carrier and fuel gases must be optimized for consistent response.

Advantages:

1. Most widely used GC detector.
2. Stable baseline due to lack of water peak.

Limitations:

Unable to detect inorganic or non-combustible compounds. Mechanism not fully understood.

1.2 Thermionic Ionization Detector (TID):

Principle: Uses a heated alkali metal source (rubidium or cesium) that ionizes nitrogen and phosphorus-containing compounds via hydrogen-rich plasma.

Operating Temperature: 400 to 800°C.

Key Features:

1. Highly selective for nitrogen and phosphorus.
2. Requires frequent source replacements and calibration due to sensitivity loss. Sensitive to specific solvents that can destabilize the detector.

Applications: Detection of pesticides and compounds containing nitrogen and phosphorus.

Limitations: Higher maintenance compared to FID.

1.3 Electron Capture Detector (ECD):

Principle: Detects electron-capturing compounds (e.g., halogenated pesticides) by measuring the reduction in ionization current produced by a radioactive beta emitter (Ni-63).

Working Mechanism: Electronegative analytes capture free electrons, decreasing the measured current.

Key Features:

1. Extremely sensitive to halogens.
2. Uses pure nitrogen or methane-argon carrier gas. Pulsed voltage operation enhances performance.

Advantages:

Very low detection limits for halogenated compounds.

Limitations:

1. Requires radioactive source and associated licensing. Sensitive to contamination by water and oxygen.
2. Baseline noise and peak distortions common.

Recent Advances: Non-radioactive pulsed discharge ECDs are under development.

1.4 Photo-Ionization Detector (PID):

Principle: Ionizes organic compounds with photons (energy 5–20 eV) without fragmentation.

Features:

1. Non-destructive, enabling coupling with other detectors. High sensitivity (5–50 times greater than FID).
2. Suitable for portable GC instruments.

Design Considerations: Requires chamber design optimization to reduce noise and improve sensitivity.

Alternative Designs: Pulsed gas discharge sources generating UV photons.

1.5 Helium Ionization Detector (HID):

Principle: Ionizes compounds with ionization potentials below 19.8 eV using helium plasma generated by radioisotope or gas discharge.

Applications: Detects permanent gases (H_2 , O_2 , N_2 , etc.), volatile organics, and some inorganics not detected by FID or TCD.

Configurations:

Standalone HID with discharge and reaction regions.
Dual function detectors (ECD/HID).

Miniaturized versions.

Operating Notes: Ultra-high purity helium is critical.
Gas discharge detectors preferred for stability.

Ionization Process: Photons generated in discharge region ionize analytes in reaction region; ions collected by electrodes.

1.6 Barrier Discharge Ionization Detector (BID):

Principle: Uses low-temperature helium plasma generated between electrodes with dielectric barriers.

Design: Quartz tube with central ring and grounded electrodes; self-limiting discharge by dielectric coating.

Advantages:

1. Fast response and reduced sample dilution.
2. Detects low molecular weight heteroatom-containing compounds poorly detected by FID.

Sensitivity Influencers: Detector temperature, makeup gas flow, background contamination.

Novelty: Emerging as a promising sensitive detector for specific compound classes.

Fig 8: Schematic diagrams of FID, TID, ECD, PID, HID, BDID

2. Bulk Physical Property Detectors:

These detectors measure physical properties of the analyte-carrier gas mixture, such as thermal conductivity.

2.1 Thermal Conductivity Detector (TCD):

Principle: Measures the change in thermal conductivity between the pure carrier gas and the analyte mixture.

Design:

Typically includes 4 small-volume cavities with tungsten or tungsten-rhenium filaments arranged in a Wheatstone bridge.

Operation:

1. Analyte elution reduces thermal conductivity, heating filaments and unbalancing the bridge to generate a voltage signal.

2. Filament temperature and thermal conductivity differential determine sensitivity.

Advantages: Universal detector, detects all compounds except the carrier gas.

Limitations:

1. Lower sensitivity relative to ionization detectors.
2. Filament oxidation limits lifespan; heating current must be optimized.

Typical Cell Volumes: 20 to 140 microliters for improved peak shape and sensitivity.

Fig 9: Schematic diagram of TCD

3. Optical Detectors:

Optical detectors utilize emission or chemiluminescence phenomena to detect specific elements or functional groups.

3.1 Flame Photometric Detector (FPD):

Principle: Uses hydrogen diffusion flames to excite sulfur, phosphorus, and sometimes tin- containing compounds, causing emission of characteristic light.

Flame Designs:

Single Flame: Combines carrier gas and air in a hydrogen atmosphere; emission zones differ for hydrocarbons and heteroatoms.

Dual Flame: Two flames in sequence increase emission intensity and selectivity.

Pulsed Flame: Periodic ignition enhances sensitivity.

Limitations: Detector response suppression (quenching) occurs; mechanism is not fully understood.

Applications: Sensitive detection of volatile sulfur and phosphorus compounds.

3.2 Gas Phase Chemiluminescence Detector (GPCD):

Principle: Selective detection of sulfur and nitrogen compounds via chemiluminescence from their oxides reacting with ozone.

Mechanism:

1. Thermal plasma converts nitrogen and sulfur compounds to nitric oxide (NO) and sulfur monoxide (SO).
2. These oxides react with ozone producing electronically excited species emitting light.

Emission Wavelengths:

1. NO₂ emits near-infrared (~1200 nm).
2. SO₂ emits between 280 and 460 nm.

Detection: Light filtered and detected by photomultiplier tubes.

Advantages: High selectivity, linear response in complex matrices.

3.3 Atomic Emission Detector (AED):

Principle: Element-selective detection of metallic elements in organometallic compounds through atomic emission spectroscopy.

Instrumentation:

1. Microwave plasma generated inside a silica discharge tube.
2. Emitted light collected by elliptical mirrors and analyzed by a photodiode array spectrometer.

Simultaneous detection limited to a 25 nm range (~4 elements).

Operating Conditions: Use of helium purge and scavenger gases (O₂, H₂, CH₄) to enhance selectivity.

Applications: Specialized laboratories for organometallic analysis.

Limitations: High maintenance and operational costs.

Fig 10: Schematic diagram of FPD, GPCD, AED

4. Electrochemical Detectors:

Electrochemical detectors generally require analytes to be in solution and depend on their electrochemical activity. Gas-phase sensing is limited for most organic compounds.

4.1 Electrolytic Conductivity Detector (ELCD):

Principle: Catalytically decomposes gas-phase analytes into small inorganic molecules that are detected by their electrolyte conductivity in a solvent.

Operation:

1. Carrier gas mixed with reagent gas (e.g., hydrogen).
2. Gas mixture passed through a heated nickel catalyst tube (850–1000°C).
3. Halogen and nitrogen compounds converted to hydrogen halides and ammonia; sulfur compounds converted to SO₂.

4. Reaction products absorbed in solvent; conductivity measured.

Enhancements: Use of chemical scrubbers (silver wire, KOH on quartz fiber) improves selectivity.

Performance:

High sensitivity and selectivity for halogen, sulfur, and nitrogen compounds.

Detection Limits: ~10⁻¹² g/s for sulfur/nitrogen; ~5×10⁻¹³ g/s for chlorine.

Challenges: Response loss, noise, poor peak shape, and linearity issues.

Trend: Declining use due to advancements in ionization and optical detectors and mass spectrometry.

Fig 11: Schematic diagram of ELCD

B. Molecular Spectroscopic Detectors:

Molecular spectroscopic detectors, primarily GC-FTIR and GC-VUV, serve as powerful tools for gas chromatography (GC) by providing both universal and selective detection through the measurement of gas-phase absorbance. These techniques are highly valued for their ability to provide qualitative structural information, such as functional group identification and isomer differentiation, which often complements mass spectrometry (MS).

1. Gas Chromatography-Fourier Transform Infrared (GC-FTIR):

GC-FTIR overcame the limitations of older dispersive IR systems by offering faster scan rates, higher sensitivity, and better precision.

Instrumentation & Interfaces:

Light-Pipe (LP): The most common online interface, utilizing a gold-coated capillary to guide IR light through the GC effluent. It is concentration-sensitive and typically achieves detection limits in the 10–100 ng range.

Matrix Isolation (MI): A mass-sensitive technique where effluent is frozen in an inert gas matrix (e.g., argon) at cryogenic temperatures (12 K). This eliminates rotational broadening, resulting in sharp, highly specific spectral features and picogram-level sensitivity.

Direct Deposition (DD): Traps effluent on a sub-ambient window (e.g., ZnSe) for analysis, offering mid-range sensitivity (~500 pg).

Current Status: While historically significant, GC-FTIR usage has declined due to hardware complexity, reliability issues, and the need for high-temperature maintenance.

2. Gas Chromatography-Vacuum Ultraviolet (GC-VUV):

A more recent development, GC-VUV measures absorption in the 120–240 nm (or up to 430 nm for newer models) range.

Key Advantages:

Universality: Nearly all chemical species (except some permanent gases) absorb strongly in the VUV region.

High Sensitivity: GC-VUV typically achieves low picogram detection limits, making it superior to standard GC-UV and GC-FTIR.

No Vacuum Required: Unlike historical VUV systems, modern benchtop units use an inert gas purge (nitrogen or argon) to remove atmospheric interferences like oxygen and water.

Advanced Features: Its rapid acquisition speed (up to 100 Hz) allows it to be coupled with fast GC and comprehensive 2D GC (GC×GC).

Table 3: Comparison between GC-FTIR and GC-VUV

Feature	FTIR (Light Pipe)	GC-VUV (VGA 100/101)
Sensitivity	Nanogram	Picogram
Detection limit	10 - 100ng	15 - 250pg
Maximum temperature	300 - 325 °C	430 °C (VGA-101)
Selectivity	High (vibrational transitions)	High (electronic transitions)

Fig 12: Schematic diagram of GC-FTIR, GC-VUV

C. Mass Spectrometric Detectors for Gas Chromatography (GC-MS):

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) is a powerful analytical technique used for the separation, identification, and quantification of volatile compounds. It combines the separation capability of gas chromatography (GC) with the structural identification ability of mass spectrometry (MS).

GC–MS IS Widely Used In Many Areas Including:

- Environmental monitoring
- Drug and doping control
- Clinical chemistry
- Food safety analysis
- Forensic science and narcotics detection
- Structural analysis of organic compounds

Modern GC–MS systems typically use capillary columns with low gas flow, allowing direct coupling with the mass spectrometer without complex interfaces.

Core Components And Interfaces:

Connecting the GC column to the MS requires specific interfaces to manage temperature and vacuum compatibility while preventing condensation.

Key Interface Types Include:

1. **Open Split Interface:** Uses a helium buffer gas and allows for column replacement without breaking the vacuum.
2. **Jet Molecular And Effusion Separators:** These enrich the analyte by removing carrier gas based on diffusion rates.
3. **Membrane Separators:** Use silicone rubber to allow organic compounds to permeate while removing the carrier gas.

Ionization Techniques:

Ionization converts neutral molecules into charged ions

The Sources Detail Several Methods:

- 1. Electron Ionization (EI):** The most common method, using 70 eV electrons to produce highly reproducible spectra ideal for library matching
- 2. Chemical Ionization (CI):** A "soft" technique using reagent gases (like methane or ammonia) to produce minimal fragmentation, which helps identify the molecular ion
- 3. Other Methods:** These include Cold EI for improved molecular ion abundance, Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization (APCI), and Photoionization using UV photons

Mass Analyzers And Operation:

The mass analyzer separates ions by their mass-to-charge ratio (m/z)

Quadrupole Mass Filters: The most common in modern systems due to their compact design and rapid scanning

Time-Of-Flight (TOF): Offers fast scanning and an unlimited mass range

High-Resolution Analyzers: Systems like the Orbitrap and FT-ICR provide extreme mass accuracy

Tandem MS (QqQ, Q-TOF): Used for highly targeted analysis and structural studies. Operational modes include Full Scan for qualitative identification and Selected Ion Monitoring (SIM) or Multiple Reaction Monitoring (MRM) for high-sensitivity quantitative analysis

Data Analysis and Sample Preparation:

Identification: Mass spectra are compared against established libraries such as NIST or Wiley

Chromatograms: Data is often viewed as a Total Ion Chromatogram (TIC) or through specific ion monitoring

Preparation: Samples often require derivatization (e.g., TMS or methyl esters) to make them more volatile, thermally stable, and detectable

APPLICATIONS AND FUTURE TRENDS:

- GC-MS is vital for environmental monitoring, forensic toxicology, food safety, and clinical chemistry.
- Future advancements are expected to focus on integration with ion mobility, faster analytical methods, and higher-resolution instrumentation.

Fig 13: Schematic diagram of GC-MS

D. Ion Mobility Spectrometry Coupled with Gas Chromatography (GC-IMS):

1. Overview And Evolution:

Ion Mobility Spectrometry (IMS) was introduced in the 1970s as an analytical technique for detecting gas-phase chemical compounds. While standalone IMS is valued for being fast, sensitive, low-cost, and portable, it suffers from low resolving power when

handling complex mixtures. To overcome this, it is frequently coupled with Gas Chromatography (GC-IMS), which provides a dual-separation mechanism that significantly improves selectivity and compound identification.

2. Fundamental Principles:

Ion Separation: Separation occurs in a drift tube under an electric field where ions collide with neutral gas molecules. An ion's velocity ($v=K \times E$) depends on its size, shape, charge, and mass

Qualitative Parameters: The Reduced Mobility Constant (K_0) allows for instrument-to-instrument comparison by normalizing for temperature and pressure.

Additionally, the Collision Cross Section (CCS) serves as a critical structural parameter for identifying specific compounds.

Data Structure: GC-IMS generates 3D datasets comprising retention time (from GC), drift time (from IMS), and signal intensity

3. Instrumentation and Variants:

An Ims Instrument Consists Of Three Primary Components:

Ionization Source: Common methods include radioactive sources (e.g., ^{63}Ni , most stable), photoionization (UV-based), and corona discharge (non-radioactive).

Drift Tube: Contains an ion gate to control entry, a drift region for separation, and a counter-flowing drift gas.

Detector: Most systems utilize a Faraday plate detector to convert ion strikes into a measurable current and spectrum. Beyond classical Drift Tube IMS (DTIMS), other variants like FAIMS (Field Asymmetric IMS) and DMS (Differential Mobility Spectrometry) are also commonly coupled with GC.

ADVANTAGES AND LIMITATIONS:

ADVANTAGES:

1. High sensitivity (ppb–ppt levels)
2. Dual separation (GC + IMS)
3. Minimal sample preparation required
4. Simultaneous positive/negative ion detection

LIMITATIONS:

1. Limited linear dynamic range
2. Lack of universal mobility databases
3. GC coupling increases total analysis time
4. Competitive ionization can cause interference

4. Data Processing and Chemometrics:

Because GC-IMS produces large, complex datasets, chemometric analysis is essential for interpretation.

Preprocessing: Includes peak picking, denoising, and baseline correction.

Analysis: Unsupervised methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) are used for pattern recognition, while supervised methods like SVM, Random Forest, or PLS-DA are employed for classification and quantification.

5. Major Applications:

Food Analysis: Detecting adulteration in honey, authenticating olive oil, and monitoring meat or egg freshness.

Clinical Diagnostics: Identifying biomarkers for cancer or Alzheimer's disease and performing non-invasive breath analysis.

Security & Environment: Monitoring chemical warfare agents, detecting explosives at airports, and screening for volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in water.

Fig 14: Schematic diagram of GC-IMS

E. Speciation and Element-Selective Detection By Gas Chromatography Plasma Spectroscopy:

Core Concept and Significance:

Elemental speciation analysis focuses on identifying the specific chemical forms of elements rather than just their total concentration. This distinction is critical because an element's toxicity, bioavailability, and environmental behavior are determined by its chemical species. Gas chromatography, when paired with element-selective plasma detectors, allows for high-resolution separation and extremely sensitive detection of these species, even in complex matrices.

Technological Landscape: Plasma-Based Detectors:

The sources highlight three primary plasma detectors used in conjunction with GC:

- 1. Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP):** Operating at temperatures between 6000–10000 K, ICP-MS is currently the dominant technique for elemental speciation. It offers multi-element detection, isotope detection capability, and ultra-trace sensitivity reaching the attogram to femtogram level. A notable feature is isotope dilution analysis, which significantly enhances quantification accuracy.
- 2. Microwave-Induced Plasma (MIP):** This is a more cost-effective alternative that uses helium as

a plasma gas. While it is less sensitive than ICP-MS, it provides superior detection for non-metals and reduced polyatomic interference.

- 3. Glow Discharge (GD):** Though primarily used for solid analysis, it can serve as a GC detector. It has the unique advantage of potentially providing both atomic and molecular information, but it remains less common in speciation studies.

Methodological Framework: Interface And Sample Preparation:

A critical component of these systems is the GC-ICPMS interface, which must maintain a high temperature via a heated transfer line and use makeup carrier gas (argon) to prevent analyte condensation during transport to the plasma. Because many analytes exist at ultra-trace levels or are nonvolatile, specific preparation is required:

- 1. Preconcentration:** Techniques such as Solid Phase Microextraction (SPME), Stir Bar Sorptive Extraction (SBSE), and cryogenic trapping are used to concentrate analytes without heavy solvent use.
- 2. Derivatization:** For nonvolatile organometallic compounds (like those of tin, mercury, and arsenic), alkylation or hydride generation is necessary to convert them into volatile forms suitable for GC separation.

KEY APPLICATIONS:

Environmental Analysis: GC-plasma spectroscopy is used to monitor Tributyltin (TBT) in seawater, methylmercury in water and soil, and volatile toxic species like phosphine in the air.

Biological and Clinical Studies: It is vital for studying selenium metabolism in plants and microorganisms, as well as detecting mercury and phosphate esters in human blood and urine.

Food Safety: The techniques are employed to differentiate between toxic and non-toxic species in seafood, such as arsenobetaine versus inorganic arsenic.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS:

The primary limitation of ICPMS is that the plasma destroys molecular structures. Therefore, the field is moving toward metallomics, which combines ICPMS with molecular mass spectrometry to retain structural information while maintaining elemental sensitivity.

Fig 15: Elemental speciation by gas chromatography with element-selective detection

Application Of Food Analysis In GC

GC is useful for analyzing nonpolar and semi-polar, volatile, and semi-volatile chemicals. Without chemical derivatization is often used for the analysis of sterols, oils, low chain fatty acids, aroma components and off flavors and many contaminants such as pesticides, industrial pollutants and certain types of drugs in food. Chemical derivatization of polar chemicals, such as amino acids, hydroxy[poly]carboxylic acids, fatty acids, phenolic compounds, sugars, vitamins, and many veterinary drugs, herbicides and natural chemical toxins is also performed to permit their analysis by GC methods.

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